

TEACHERS' PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES, CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICES IN TEACHING MUSIC: BASES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIAL

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Teachers' Pedagogical Approaches, Content Knowledge and Practices in Teaching Music: Bases for the Development of Instructional Material

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Abstract

This descriptive-correlational study determined the teachers' pedagogical approaches, content knowledge, and practices in teaching music as bases for the development of instructional material in School Year 2024-2025. A researcher-made questionnaire on teachers' pedagogical approaches, content knowledge, and practices was used to gather data from the respondents which were classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization. The statistical tools used were frequency count, percentage, mean, Mann Whitney U-test, Kruskal Wallis, and Spearman rho with the aid of computers' Statistical Package for Social Sciences Software (SPSS). The level of significance was set at 0.05 alpha. Result revealed that most of the music teacher in the Schools Division of Iloilo Province were female, 20 to 30 years old, bachelor's degree holders, most of them came from first congressional district and generalist. The level of teachers' content knowledge in teaching music when taken as a whole was high. In addition, in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, and specialization was high, only in congressional district was noted as moderate. There were no significant differences in teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district and specialization. Furthermore, No significant differences in teachers' content knowledge in teaching music when classified according to age and educational attainment however, a significant difference were noted in congressional district. There were no significant differences in teachers' practices when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district and specialization. Notably, a Significant relationship existed among the teachers' pedagogical approaches, content knowledge and practices in teaching music. These findings offer a valuable basis for developing instructional resources that can further strengthen music education in different schools.

Keywords: *pedagogical approaches, content knowledge, practices, teaching music, instructional material*

Introduction

Music education plays a vital role in the overall development of students. It increases our cognitive capabilities, encourages emotional output and enhances social skills. It is believed that, according to the study of Hallam, (2020), using music in conjunction with learning subjects produces better results for academic as well as personal development from a musical point. Not only that, it can also raise the intelligence quotient of children making their language skills finesse early on in life, their spatial-temporal abilities and even math; as study of Guhn, et.,al (2020).

However, the reality of teaching music often falls short of this ideal. Many music educators face significant challenges, including limited funding, inadequate resources, and large class sizes that hinder personalized instruction. Schools frequently lack of sufficient instruments, advanced technology and most of all is alignment of the subject taught by the teachers. Findings of EDCOM 2024 states that the alignment with personal and professional growth of the teachers should be prioritized by the government in order to ensure quality education the learners deserve.

In K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum Framework of Music and Arts Education, the design of curricula is described as student centered, based on spiral progression of process, concepts and skills and grounded in performance-based learning, DepEd (2013). It is therefore ideal that music should be taught by competent music educators so that pupils would be engaged in learning music through active involvement and participation. However, in most elementary schools, children are usually taught by "generalist" teachers who are expected to teach all curricular subjects, including music. As a subject, Music may appeal to be one of the most challenging subjects to teach by a generalist teacher who does not have an expertise or any background in music.

Thus, until now, the researcher seldom sees music teacher who are using different approaches and practices in teaching music. Most often they directly let the learners sing the song all throughout the period as their practice and the competencies which are required by the curriculum have not met.

Considering the importance of teaching music to the generalist teacher, the researcher was inspired to conduct a study to determine the teachers' pedagogical approaches, content knowledge and practices in teaching music as bases for the development of instructional materials in the Schools Division of Iloilo.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the teachers' pedagogical approaches, content knowledge and practices in teaching music in the Schools Division of Iloilo, Philippines for School Year 2024-2025 as bases for the development of instructional material. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization?
2. What are the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when taken as a whole and when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization?
3. What is the level of teachers' content knowledge in teaching music when taken as a whole and when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization?
4. What are the teachers' practices in teaching music when taken as a whole and when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization?
5. Are there significant differences in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization?
6. Are there significant differences in the level of teachers' content knowledge in teaching music when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization?
7. Are there significant differences in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization?
8. Are there significant relationships among teachers' pedagogical approaches, content knowledge, and practices in teaching music?
9. Based on the findings of the study, what instructional material can be developed?

Literature Review

On Teachers' Pedagogical Approaches in Teaching Music

For teachers to effectively and enrichingly teach music to their pupils, their pedagogical approaches and content understanding are essential to use the latest tools available in their work to engage students. To engage students in learning, one needs to be innovative and new ideas should be introduced so that students get excited about what they are learning. The use of varied and latest pedagogical approaches like technology integration in music education. It transformed music education by providing new tools and resources for teaching and learning. Digital technologies, such as music notation software, recording equipment, and online platforms, enhance accessibility, creativity, and collaboration in music instruction, Brown and Lee (2023). Therefore the need to equip the teachers with the necessary skills on how to incorporate educational technology in the pedagogy of teaching, and to provide the educators with the resources needed in doing so is viewed imperative.

Concretization of the principle of interdisciplinarity in pedagogical-music research allows combining interdisciplinary and hermeneutic approaches, which organically corresponds to the nature of art education. In the framework of phenomenological approach, music is positioned as a distinctive phenomenon that comprehends the immense and creates a sensual picture of the world. It is shown that, in contrast to the competence approach, which directs the efforts of researchers to the formation of professional and personal qualities of the teacher, the interdisciplinary approach primarily involves optimization of the curriculum. Interdisciplinary coordination is considered as flexible and consistent use of all its components in a real learning process that primarily involves optimization of the curriculum. Interdisciplinary coordination, based on the allocation of related elements in the content of subjects of historical-theoretical and music-performing blocks, provides formation of conditions of generalized ways of actions and their use in various activities (educational, performing and didactic) independently, flexibly, and creatively, Nikolai, H. et.,al.(2020).

According to Barrett, J. and Webster, P. (2020), music is more prevalent than ever in the lives of people of all ages in our quickly evolving and globally interconnected society. Nonetheless, it is noteworthy that within this particular context, "many of the formal methods by which we teach this music are mired in antiquated theories and practices. New approaches to the conceptualization and implementation of music education that honor historical accomplishments while simultaneously anticipating novel paradigms are sorely needed". The necessity to rethink teaching and learning pedagogy for education in the twenty-first century has emerged as a result of the growing and changing needs and requirements of society. Education and government authorities continue to express concern about the significant disparity between what occurs in the classroom and what occurs in real-life contexts .

Studies have suggested that teachers are one of the most important indicators of whether a classroom exhibits high-or low-quality instruction, Poulter, V. and Cook, T. (2020). Nevertheless, there is no commonly identified and globally agreed-upon set of musical competences required for early childhood teachers. Research on teacher competency in early childhood music education is scarce and suggestions in the literature for improving music teacher education are often vague. In the global context, the National Association for the Education of Young Children (2019) suggested that the early childhood teachers should be familiar with a variety of materials and tools in teaching each of the art forms.

Sušić's (2021) recent study has revealed some perceived musical competencies by the early childhood teachers in Vienna, they were: music literacy, playing lead instruments, leading creative music activities, singing songs to a melodic instrument, active listening to music, playing Orff instruments, leading games involving singing, crafting children's instruments, and working with gifted children.

On Teachers' Content Knowledge in Teaching Music

Content knowledge is important not only in comprehending a text but also in learning from it. Knowledge is expanded when it

is integrated with the textbase (i.e., constructing the situation model), because it is how new information learned from text is stored in a long-term memory. Moreover, content knowledge also aids in the processing of information from a text in memory (Willingham, 2017). Content knowledge enables information to be chunked or stored together in working memory, freeing up space for other information to be understood or learned from the text Cabell, S. et.,al.(2020).

Content knowledge was introduced and defined by Shulman (1986) as teachers' ways of representing and formulating subject matter knowledge to facilitate student learning. Shulman (1987) also described PCK as "that special amalgam of content and pedagogy that is uniquely the province of teachers, their special form of professional understanding." According to Shulman (1987), content and pedagogical knowledge should be integrated and not seen as competing. The most important difference between a teacher and a scientist is pedagogical content knowledge. For example, a science or mathematics teacher differs from a scientist in how he or she organizes and presents knowledge to students. The term content knowledge refers to the body of knowledge and information that teachers teach and that students are expected to learn in a given subject or content area such as English language arts, mathematics, science, or social studies. It encompasses factual knowledge, conceptual understanding, and procedural skills within a particular discipline or field of study. In 1987, Shulman continued his work by organizing teachers' knowledge base into seven categories. These are (1) content knowledge, (2) general pedagogical knowledge, (3) curriculum knowledge, (4) pedagogical content knowledge, (5) knowledge of learners and their characteristics, (6) knowledge of educational contexts, and (7) knowledge of educational ends, purposes, and values. Content knowledge, which Shulman (1987) described as the first category of teachers' knowledge base, includes knowledge, understanding, skills, and dispositions that should be learned and grounded in the amassed literature and study within a content area.

Tee, M. et.,al.(2023) investigated the knowledge required for teaching based on the mathematical problems that appeared during such, focusing on the manner through which teachers showed students the way to solve problems, answered students' questions, and assessed students' work. Primary data for this work came from an entire year of teaching mathematics in a third-grade classroom, which included videotapes and audiotapes of lessons, transcripts, student work, homework, quizzes, and the teacher's plans, notes, and reflections. After individual teaching episodes were reviewed and instruction was studied over time, the authors concluded that Shulman's content knowledge could be further divided into common content knowledge and specialized content knowledge. Common content knowledge was defined as the mathematical knowledge and skills that others have and utilize in areas other than teaching. Specialized content knowledge, on the other hand, was defined as the mathematical knowledge and skills that are unique to teaching and not typically needed in areas other than teaching mathematics. In addition, teachers must have unpacked this knowledge to be able to make content visible to and learnable by students. An example of this would be explaining the need to invert and multiply in the division of fractions. Other examples would include accountants who calculate and reconcile numbers or engineers who use mathematics to model properties of materials.

According to Smith, A. et.,al. (2021), content knowledge includes both declarative knowledge (facts and concepts) and procedural knowledge (skills and strategies), essential for effective teaching and learning. In addition to resources like textbooks and worksheets, technology equips educators with various tools to help students develop a better understanding of the material, Concordia Texas University, (2023).

Pedagogical Content Knowledge plays an important role in classroom instructions. It is an educational term that describes several interconnected domains of knowledge that are useful to the teacher teaching in a school or in an out of school context. The most important domains are subject specific content knowledge and knowledge of the pedagogy used in teaching a subject. In the teaching and learning process, a PCK involves teachers' competence in delivering the conceptual approach, relational understanding and adaptive reasoning of the subject matter. Without a full grasp of PCK, teachers may face difficulty in teaching the subject effectively. Teachers should be knowledgeable in the content areas and pedagogy for which they are responsible to teach, without this, the students may face difficulty in their learning. Further, the study article has shown that improving teachers' PCK could lead to improvement in teachers' instructional practices, and consequently, students' academic achievement, Jacob, et.,al.(2020).

Practices in Teaching Music

The effective music education relies on implementing best practices that foster student engagement, skill development, and a deep appreciation for music. Recent research emphasizes several key strategies and methodologies that contribute to successful music teaching and learning experiences. The learning environment is more dynamic than ever before, and as a result, today's learners are learning in a way that's very different from how our educational system was originally designed. Teachers need to tailor instruction to meet the diverse needs of students is crucial in music education. Differentiated instruction allows educators to adjust teaching methods, materials, and assessment strategies based on students' musical abilities, interests, and learning styles, Wiggins,T. (2023).

Barrett, J. (2022) Music is enjoyable for both children and teachers and holds such potential for creating connections between the teachers and children while providing opportunities for learning and discovery and enhancing academic, and social skills. With strategic planning, teachers, directors, and programs can use the best practices for music-making to support music an integral part of the preschool classroom and children's learning experiences.

Bylica, K. et.al (2022) states that teaching future educators how to begin conversations with administrators might help them advocate for support they need to engage in risk-taking and critical questioning as a fundamental element of their teaching practice. Teacher

educators might create open forums wherein practicing teachers, administrators, and future educators partner together, and even work with K–12 students, to consider how pedagogical creativity may serve as a way of supporting responsive and care-oriented educational practice.

Music teacher education programs might also highlight risk-taking, particularly when risks are both strategic and responsive, as a foundational element of one’s pedagogy. Practice in risk-taking can help avoid closed thinking and encourage future teachers to engage with pedagogical agility, thus helping them see risk as a necessary and welcome part of everyday practice, rather than solely a response to periods of unpredictability. As identified most distinctly by Christen and Jackie in this study, choosing to engage in practices that may be perceived as “risky,” both within and beyond contexts of rapid change, may help educators build their own sense of identity as capable, creative, and responsive professionals.

Culturally responsive pedagogy involves teaching in ways that are responsive to how different culturally specific knowledge bases impact learning. It is a pedagogy that recognizes the importance of including students’ cultural references Preface in all aspects of learning. Music educators are in a unique position to fully implement these practices in their classrooms given the intimate connection between music and culture McKoy, C. et.,al. (2022).

It is therefore significant how effectively music teachers consider their practice within the intensely personal process of consistently aspiring to design rich musical curricula for the musical development of young people. Music curriculum design is therefore a critical fulcrum around which classroom music education operates and merits greater consideration and discussion in the literature of the field. Such a developmental discourse is essential in future theoretical developments to support musical learning and facilitate critical engagements between young people and their teachers, thus enabling musical learning in a classroom context, Anderson, R. (2022).

Barton, G. (2021) came up with implications for the development of contemporary music teaching and learning practices. These include: providing insight into the way culture potentially influences how instrumental music is taught in other contexts and situations such as classroom music; enabling teachers to reflect on their instrumental music teaching practice and place it within a broader social and cultural context; providing teachers with a basis for a way of assessing and responding to cultural influence in instrumental teaching processes and practices; providing greater opportunities for teachers of instrumental music to utilise traditions other than their own to teach musical concepts – ‘teaching music culturally’; and, providing teachers with a greater repertoire of skills and techniques to work more flexibly with the cultural backgrounds and experiences of learners in their tutelage. In regard to formal music education practices, it is critical to note that music knowledge be demonstrated, recorded and assessed in various ways. These processes are integral to music teaching and learning practices and are grounded in a music’s cultural genesis.

Methodology

Respondents

The descriptive-correlational research method was used as the research design of the study. Respondents of the study were all one hundred seventy (170) teachers teaching music of first to fifth congressional district in the schools division of Iloilo province for the school year 2024-2025.

The independent variables were age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization. The dependent variables were the teachers’ pedagogical approaches, content knowledge, and practices.

Instrument

A researcher-made questionnaire on teachers’ pedagogical approaches, content knowledge, and practices was used to gather data from the respondents. They were classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization.

The validity of the questionnaire was determined by presenting the questionnaire to the panel of experts with the use of the 8-Point Criteria of Good and Scates. The reliability was tested on 30 generalist and core teachers from Molo Elementary School who were not part of the actual respondents but possessed similar attributes to the actual respondents and having the reliability results of cronbach alpha coefficient.

Procedure

The researchers first ask permission to the schools division superintendent to conduct the study and upon the approval, the researchers then proceed to the locale of the study to ask for the approval of the conduct of the study. After the research instrument was established to be valid and reliable, the researcher sought the concurrence of the Dean of the Graduate School to administer the instrument to the respondents. The researcher asked the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd, Schools Division of Iloilo Province to conduct the study to all teachers teaching music in the first to fifth congressional district.

A permit was distributed to the school Principal of the different schools in the province of Iloilo. After the administration, retrieval of the accomplished questionnaire followed. The data were collected, organized and tabulated. Computation, analysis and interpretations were done using appropriate tools through the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software.

Ethical Considerations

The participants were informed about the research objectives, methods and potentials risks by the researchers. A written informed consent from all participants before collecting any data were secured. The researcher guaranteed the anonymity and confidentiality of participants by using pseudonyms and securely storing all collected data.

The researchers made it clear to all participants that participation in the research is fully voluntary, and they were free to quit at any time.

The data were gathered using ethical and non-intrusive methods, ensuring that no personal or sensitive information is disclosed without consent. The researchers also maintained the accuracy and integrity of collected data and report findings truthfully, regardless of the outcome.

Disclose any potential conflicts of interest, such as personal or financial relationships with the subjects of the study that may influence the research.

Clearly reported the methodology, data collection instruments, and data analysis techniques used in the research. Share any limitations and potential biases in the study's design or execution.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets data to determine the teachers' pedagogical approaches, content knowledge, and practices in teaching music as bases for the development of instructional material in the Schools Division of Iloilo, Philippines for the School Year 2024-2025.

Profile of Music Teachers

Table 1 shows the profile of the music teachers in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district and specialization using the frequency count and percentages.

Based on the table below, it showed that out of the 170 respondents, when the respondents were classified as to sex, there were 40 (23.5%) males and there were 130 (76.5%) females.

When classified according to age, those who belonged on age bracket of 20-30 years old were 66 (38.8%) , 47 (27.6%) belonged to above 31-40 years of age, 41-50 years old gained 39 (22.9%) while 18 (10.6%) belonged to 51-60 years of age. In addition, when the respondents were grouped as to educational attainment, those with bachelors degree were 93 (54.7%), those with masteral units were 49 (28.8%), those with master's degree were 24 (14.1%) those with doctorate units were 3 (1.8 %) and those with doctorate degree were 1 (0.6%). Furthermore, when grouped into congressional district, there were 38 (22.4%) in the first congressional district, 37 (21.8 %) in the second congressional district, 27 (15.9%) were noted. 34 (20.0%) from fourth congressional district and were 34 (20.0 %) and fifth congressional district. When Classified as to the specialization those general education teachers were 116 (68.2 %) and 54 (31.8%) were in the core subject teachers.

Lastly, data revealed that majority of the Muisic teachers in the Schools Division of Iloilo Province were within the age bracket of 20-30 years old, female were the majority, with bachelors degree, teaching in different congressional district and public schools.

Table 1. *Profile of the Music Teachers in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district and specialization*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
<i>Age</i>		
20-30	66	38.8
31-40	47	27.6
41-50	39	22.9
51-60	18	10.6
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	40	23.5
Female	130	76.5
<i>Educational Attainment</i>		
Bachelors Degree	93	21.6
Masteral Units	49	40.2
Master's Degree	24	29.4
Doctorate Units	3	1.8
Doctorate Degree	1	.6
<i>Congressional District</i>		
1st District	38	22.4
2nd District	37	21.8
3rd District	27	15.9

4th District	34	20.0
5th District	34	20.0
Specialization	116	68.2
General Education	54	31.8
Core Subjects		
Total	170	100.0

Table 2 shows the teachers’ pedagogical approaches in teaching music, when taken as a whole, the researcher used the frequency count, percentage and rank.

As the results show, Integration to other disciplines in music education is the most often used strategy, as seen in table 3 when all responses are considered. This means that integrated approach to teaching music in which teachers incorporate elements of social studies, arithmetic, and language to enhance their pupils’ musical comprehension. Teachers give pupils a more comprehensive and contextualized understanding of music through the use of interdisciplinary teaching.

Table 2. Teachers’ pedagogical approaches in teaching music when taken as a whole

Items	f	%	Rank
Incorporate other disciplines to my music teaching.	159	93.5	1
Show learners how to properly sing the song through modeling	157	92.4	2
Use my voice as the primary instrument for teaching a song	152	89.4	3
Let pupils interpret the song or other aspects of the music through a blend of acting, dancing and singing.	151	89.4	4
Let my learners improvise instruments using localize materials and engage in musical activities	150	88.2	5
Use solfege as ear training in familiarizing the different notes.	149	87.6	6
Use hand sign in acquiring pitch, sight reading and learning primary rhythms to the learners.	147	86.5	7
Conduct song analysis by asking pupils about the title, author, time signature and key signature of the song.	146	85.9	8
Use props and toys for learners to discover basic musical concepts.	144	84.7	9
Conduct rhythmic syllabication to the learners.	142	83.5	10
Use games for plotting the notes and rests.	137	80.6	11.5
Organized classroom environment that enables the learners to acquire music rudiments by exploring through the sense of touch.	137	80.6	11.5
Let my learners create a simple song composition.	135	79.4	13
Use tonic solfege system (fixed-do) so that learners can develop perfect pitch.	120	70.6	14
Assess musical progress and understanding of my learners through musical interdependence and discovery.	112	69.9	15

Teachers’ Pedagogical Approaches in Teaching Music When Classified according to Age

Table 4 shows the teachers’ pedagogical approaches in teaching Music when classified according to age was determined using frequency, percentage, and rank.

Table 4. Teachers’ Pedagogical Approaches in Teaching Music When Classified According to Age

Items	20-30			31-40			41-50			51-60		
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank
MUSIC												
Use hand sign in acquiring pitch, sight reading and learning primary rhythms to the learners.	57	86.4	9.5	41	87.2	2.5	33	84.6	10	16	88.9	9
Use games for plotting notes and rests.	52	78.8	12.5	37	78.7	9.5	33	84.6	10	15	83.3	12
Show learners how to properly sing the song through modeling.	61	92.4	2	42	89.4	1	37	94.9	3	17	94.4	5
Let my learners improvise instruments using localize materials and engage in musical activities.	58	87.9	6.5	38	80.9	7.5	38	97.4	1.5	16	88.9	9
Incorporate other disciplines to my music teaching.	62	93.9	1	41	87.2	2.5	38	97.4	1.5	18	100.0	1.5
Use my voice as the primary instrument for teaching a song.	59	89.4	4.5	40	85.1	4	36	92.3	4	17	94.4	5
Use props and toys for learners to discover basic musical concepts.	57	86.4	9.5	36	76.6	11.5	34	87.2	7	17	94.4	5
Use the tonic solfege system (fixed-do) so that learners can develop perfect pitch.	43	65.2	14.5	32	68.1	14	30	76.9	14	15	83.3	12
Organized classroom environment that enables the learners to acquire music rudiments by exploring through the sense of touch.	52	78.8	12.5	36	76.6	11.5	31	79.5	13	18	100.0	1.5
Use solfege as ear training in familiarizing the different notes.	43	65.2	14.5	27	57.4	15	29	74.4	15	13	72.2	14.5
Assess musical progress and understanding of my learners through musical independence and discovery	59	89.4	4.5	39	83.0	5.5	34	87.2	7	17	94.4	5
Let my learners create a simple song composition.	57	86.4	9.5	33	70.2	13	32	82.1	12	13	72.2	14.5
Conduct song analysis by asking pupils about the title, author, time signature and key signature of the song.	58	87.9	6.5	38	80.9	7.5	34	87.2	7	16	88.9	9
Conduct rhythmic syllabication to the learners.	57	86.4	9.5	37	78.7	9.5	33	84.6	10	15	83.3	12
Let pupils interpret the song or other aspects of the music through a blend of acting, dancing and singing.	60	90.9	3	39	83.0	5.5	35	89.7	5	17	94.4	5

As presented in the table, incorporate other disciplines into music teaching ranked first for teachers aged (20-30 years old), while in the age bracket of (31-40) mostly their choice is to show learners how properly sing a song through modeling, in this age they prioritize direct demonstration or modeling in their approach, most likely due to their experiences in recognizing the importance of clear and guided instruction, on the other hand teachers aged (41-50 years old) chose to let learners improvise instruments using localized materials in musical activities, this simply shows that teachers in this age group highly value creative and experiential learning and lastly, older teachers (51-60 years old) picked incorporate othe disciplines into music and organize a classroom environment for exploring music through the sense of touch. This shows that teachers on this age bracket show a string preference for both interdisciplinary teaching and tactile learning environment.

This shows that pedagogical approaches in music teaching can vary significantly depending on the age of the teacher, with each group bringing unique strengths and perspective in the classroom.

Table 5 shows the teachers’ pedagogical approaches in teaching Music when classified according to sex was determined using frequency, percentage, and rank.

Data revealed that male respondents chose to incorporate other disciplines to their music teaching and use their voice as the primary instrument for teaching a song, female on the other hand did the same choice in incorporating other discipline to their music teaching. This shows that both male and female teachers prioritize interdisciplinay learning approaches, however male teachers lean more towards vocal and performance- based methods. Both sets of approaches contribute to a well-rounded and engaging music education.

This result is supported by the findings of Nikolai, et.,al.(2020) which states that interdisciplinary coordination is considered as flexible and consistent use of all its components in a real learning process that primarily involves optimization of the curriculum.

Interdisciplinary coordination, based on the allocation of related elements in the content of subjects of historical-theoretical and music-performing blocks, provides formation of conditions of generalized ways of actions and their use in various activities (educational, performing and didactic) independently, flexibly, and creatively.

Table 5. Teachers’ pedagogical aprooces in teaching music when classified according to sex

Items	Male			Female		
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank
MUSIC						
Use hand sign in acquiring pitch, sight reading and learning primary rhythms to the learners.	36	90.0	6.5	111	85.4	7.5
Use games for plotting notes and rests.	35	87.5	10	102	78.5	13
Show learners how to properly sing the song through modeling.	36	90.0	6.5	121	93.1	2
Let my learners improvise instruments using localize materials and engage in musical activities.	35	87.5	10.0	115	88.5	3.5
Incorporate other disciplines to my music teaching.	37	92.5	2.5	122	93.8	1
Use my voice as the primary instrument for teaching a song.	37	92.5	2.5	115	88.5	3.5
Use props and toys for learners to discover basic musical concepts.	36	90.0	6.5	108	83.1	9
Use the tonic solfege system (fixed-do) so that learners can develop perfect pitch.	25	62.5	14	95	73.1	14
Organized classroom environment that enables the learners to acquire music rudiments by explporing through the sense of touch.	31	77.5	12	106	81.5	10.5
Use solfege as ear training in familiarizing the different notes.	27	67.5	13	85	65.4	15
Assess musical progress and understanding of my learners through musical independence and discovery.	37	92.5	2.5	112	86.2	6
Let my learners create a simple song composition.	32	80.0	11	103	79.2	12
Conduct song analysis by asking pupils about the title, author, time signature and key signature of the song.	35	87.5	10.0	111	85.4	7.5
Conduct rhythmic syllabication to the leaners.	36	90.0	6.5	106	81.5	10.5
Let pupils interpret the song or other aspects of the music through a blend of acting, dancing and singing.	37	92.5	2.5	114	87.7	5

Table 6 shows the teachers’ pedagogical approaches in teaching Music when classified according to educational attainment was determined using frequency, percentage, and rank.

Data revealed that bachelor’s degree holder teachers and those with master’s units chose to incorporate other discipline into music teaching, while those master’s degree holder teachers yielded in showing learners how to properly sing the song through modeling and use props and toys to teach basic musical concepts. Those teachers with doctorate units and doctorate degree holder used the multiple approach in teaching music.

This means that teachers at all educational levels value the interdisciplinay approaches, more advanced teachers are increasingly inclined to use practical , hands- on methods, reflecting progression in teaching expertise as educational attainment upgraded.

Table 6. Teachers' Pedagogical Approaches in Teaching Music When Classified according to Educational Attainment

Items	Bachelor's Degree			W/Master's Units			Master's Degree			W/ Doctorate Units			Doctorate Degree		
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank
MUSIC															
Use hand sign in acquiring pitch, sight reading and learning primary rhythms to the learners.	82	88.2	8	42	85.7	6	19	79.2	7.5	100.0	7	1	100.0	8	
Use games for plotting notes and rests.	80	86.0	9.5	38	77.6	12	15	62.5	11.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Show learners how to properly sing the song through modeling.	88	94.6	3	43	87.8	3.5	22	91.7	1.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Let my learners improvise instruments using localize materials and engage in music activities.	83	89.2	7	42	85.7	6	21	87.5	3	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Incorporate other disciplines to my music teaching.	90	96.8	1	45	91.8	1	20	83.3	5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Use my voice as the primary instrument for teaching a song.	85	91.4	4.5	41	83.7	8.5	22	91.7	4.5	2	66.7	14.5	1	100.0	8
Use props and toys for learners to discover basic musical concepts.	85	91.4	4.5	42	85.7	6	14	58.3	1.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Use the tonic solfège system (fixed-do) so that learners can develop perfect pitch.	69	74.2	14	34	69.4	13.5	13	54.2	13	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Organized classroom environment that enables the learners to acquire music rudiment by exploring through the sense of touch.	79	84.9	11	39	79.6	10.5	15	62.5	14	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Use solfège as ear training in familiarizing the different notes.	67	72.0	15	30	61.2	15	11	45.8	11.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Assess musical progress and understanding of my learners through musical independence and discovery	89	95.7	2	39	79.6	10.5	17	70.8	15	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Let my learners create a simple song composition.	0	6.0	9.5	34	69.4	13.5	17	70.8	9.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Conduct song analysis by asking pupils about the title, author, time signature and key signature of the song.	3	3.9	12.5	44	89.8	2	20	83.5	4.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Conduct rhythmic syllabication to the learners.	8	3.9	12.5	41	83.7	8.5	19	79.2	7.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Let pupils interpret the song or other aspects of the music through a blend of acting, dancing and singing.	4	90.3	6	43	87.8	3.5	20	83.3	4.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8

Table 7 shows the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching Music when classified according to congressional district was determined using frequency, percentage, and rank.

Data revealed that those teachers in the first congressional district chose to incorporate other disciplines into music teaching, while the second district teachers prioritize the use of props and toys to teach basic music concepts and assess musical progress through independence and discovery, third congressional district on the other hand chose to use their voice as their primary instrument for teaching a song. Fourth congressional district prioritized both incorporating other discipline into teaching music and showing learners how to properly sing through modeling. Lastly fifth congressional district chose to use their voice as their primary instrument for teaching a song.

The result shows that while there are some common themes across the districts, such as interdisciplinary teaching, each district's unique top-ranked approaches reflects localized preferences and priorities in music education. These differences offer insights into how local and cultural context may shape teaching strategies and educational outcomes.

The result of this study is supported by the study of Szelei, et.,al. (2020) which states that school leaders in every district should reinforce the needs by familiarising teachers with meaningful pedagogical contents. Such are, for example, multilingual pedagogies, culturally relevant teaching, pedagogies of student voice and empowerment that support teachers in pedagogically conceptualising their practices, and at the same time attempt to avoid othering by focusing on students and improving student learning.

Table 7. Teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to Congressional District

Items	1 st District			2 nd District			3 rd District			4 th District			5 th District		
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank
MUSIC															
Use hand sign in acquiring pitch, sight reading and learning primary rhythms to the learners.	33	86.8	6	31	83.8	7.5	24	88.9	4.5	29	85.3	8.5	30	88.2	9.5
Use games for plotting notes and rests.	35	92.1	3	31	83.8	7.5	22	81.5	9	21	61.8	14	28	82.4	13.5
Show learners how to properly sing the song through modeling.	35	92.1	3	32	86.5	4.5	26	96.3	2.5	31	91.2	5	33	97.1	2
Let my learners improvise instruments using localize materials and engage in musical activities.	32	84.2	8.5	31	83.8	7.5	23	85.2	6.5	33	97.1	2	31	91.2	6
Incorporate other disciplines to my music teaching.	36	94.7	1	33	89.2	3	26	96.3	2.5	33	97.1	2	31	91.2	6
Use my voice as the primary instrument for teaching a song.	30	78.9	11.5	30	81.1	10	27	100.0	1	31	91.2	5	34	100.0	1
Use props and toys for learners to discover basic musical concepts.	30	78.9	11.5	34	91.9	1.5	21	77.8	11.5	27	79.4	12	32	94.1	3
Use the tonic solfège system (fixed-do) so that learners can develop perfect pitch.	23	60.5	15	27	73.0	13.5	19	70.4	13.5	25	73.5	13	26	76.5	6
Organized classroom environment that enables the learners to acquire music rudiments by exploring through the sense of touch.	31	81.6	10	28	75.7	11.5	21	77.8	11.5	28	82.4	11	29	85.3	11.5
Use solfège as ear training in familiarizing the different notes.	25	65.8	14	24	64.9	15	17	63.0	15	20	58.8	15	26	76.5	15
Assess musical progress and understanding of my learners through musical independence and discovery	33	86.8	6	34	91.9	1.5	23	85.2	6.5	29	85.3	8.5	30	88.2	9.5
Let my learners create a simple song composition.	28	73.7	13	31	83.6	7.5	19	70.4	13.5	29	85.3	8.5	28	82.4	13.5
Conduct song analysis by asking pupils about the title, author, time signature and key signature of the song.	32	84.2	8.5	28	75.7	11.5	24	88.9	4.5	33	97.1	2	29	85.3	11.5
Conduct rhythmic syllabication to the learners.	33	86.8	6	27	73.0	13.5	22	81.5	9	29	85.3	8.5	31	91.2	6
Let pupils interpret the song or other aspects of the music through a blend of acting, dancing and singing.	35	92.1	3	32	86.5	4.5	22	81.5	9	31	91.2	5	31	91.2	6

Table 8 shows the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching Music when classified according to specialization was determined using frequency, percentage, and rank.

Data revealed when it comes to specialization general education teachers chose to show learners how to properly sing the song through modeling while those core subject teachers preferred to incorporate other disciplines into music teaching.

This shows that these differences really highlight the distinct approaches that each group brings to music education. With general education teachers preferred to a more direct instructional technique while core teachers offering broader, more integrative method. Both approaches complement each other in the larger educational framework, ensuring learners received both foundational skills and creative, intellectual engagement in music.

This result is supported by the study Brown and Lee (2023) which states that for teachers to effectively and enrichingly teach music to their pupils, their pedagogical approaches and content understanding are essential to teachers to use the latest tools available in their work to engage students. To engage students in learning, one needs to be innovative and new ideas should be introduced so that students get excited about what they are learning.

Table 8. Teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to Specialization

Items	General Education			Core Subject		
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank
MUSIC						
Use hand sign in acquiring pitch, sight reading and learning primary rhythms to the learners.	102	87.9	4	45	83.3	8.5
Use games for plotting notes and rests.	94	81.0	12	43	79.6	11.5
Show learners how to properly sing the song through modeling.	107	92.2	1	50	92.6	4
Let my learners improvise instruments using localize materials and engage in musical activities.	99	85.3	7.5	51	94.4	2.5
Incorporate other disciplines to my music teaching.	105	90.5	3	54	100	1
Use my voice as the primary instrument for teaching a song.	106	91.4	2	46	85.2	7
Use props and toys for learners to discover basic musical concepts.	99	85.3	7.5	45	83.3	8.5
Use the tonic solfege system (fixed-do) so that learners can develop perfect pitch.	79	68.1	14	41	75.9	13.5
Organized classroom environment that enables the learners to acquire music rudiments by exploring through the sense of touch.	96	82.8	11	41	75.9	13.5
Use solfege as ear training in familiarizing the different notes.	76	65.5	15	46	66.7	15
Assess musical progress and understanding of my learners through musical independence and discovery.	100	86.2	5.5	49	90.7	5
Let my learners create a simple song composition.	92	79.3	13	43	79.6	11.5
Conduct song analysis by asking pupils about the title, author, time signature and key signature of the song.	99	85.3	7.5	47	87.0	6
Conduct rhythmic syllabication to the learners.	98	84.5	10	44	81.5	10
Let pupils interpret the song or other aspects of the music through a blend of acting, dancing and singing.	100	86.2	5.5	51	94.4	2.5

Table shows 9 shows the level of teachers' content knowledge in teaching music when taken as a whole and when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district and specialization.

Table 9. Level of Teachers' Content Knowledge in Teaching Music when taken as a Whole and when Classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district and specialization

Variables	Mean	Description
Age		
20-30	9.82	High
31-40	9.13	High
41-50	9.85	High
51-60	9.72	High
Sex		
Male	9.90	High
Female	9.54	High
Educational Attainment		
Bachelors Degree	9.40	High
W/ Master's Units	10.33	High
Master's Degree	9.04	High
W/ Doctorate Units	11.33	High
Doctorate Degree	5.00	Low
Congressional District		
1st District	10.37	High
2nd District	7.78	Moderate
3rd District	10.74	High
4th District	9.41	High

5th District	10.12	High
Specialization		
General Education	9.73	High
Core Subject	9.43	high
Overall Mean	9.62	high

Scale of Means: 12.01-15.00 Very High(VH); 9.01-12.00 High (H); 6.01-9.00 Moderate (M); 3.01-6.00 Low (L); 0-3.00 Very Low (VL)

It was explained in this table that the level of teachers’ content knowledge when taken as a whole (M=9.96) was high as a results showed that they were highly knowledgeable. As to age, the level of content knowledge in teaching music aged 21 to 30 years old (M=9.82), 31 to 40 years old (M=9.13), 41 to 50 years old (M=9.85) and 51 to 60 years old (M=9.72) was also high as the results showed they were highly knowledgeable. As to sex the level of content knowledge of male (M=9.90), femle (9.54) were high as well.As to the educational attainment of teachers teaching music who were bachelors degree holder (M=9.40), w/ master’s degree units (M=10.33), Master’s degree holder (M=9.04), w/ doctorate units (M=11.33) were higly knowledgeable, however those with Doctorate degree (M=5.00) noted as low. As to congressional district’s level of content knowledge who are in the first district (M=10.37), which is highly knowledgeable, second district (M=7.78) moderately knowledgeable, third district (M=10.74), fourth district (M=9.41), and fift district (M=10.12) showed a high level of content knowledge. As to specialization, general education teachers (M=9.73), core subject teachers (M=9.43) were also high in content knowledge.

This result is supported by the study of Jacob, et.,al.(2020). Which states that in the teaching and learning process, a pedagogical content knowledge involves teachers’ competence in delivering the conceptual approach, relational understanding and adaptive reasoning of the subject matter. Without a full grasp of pedagogocal content knowledge teachers may face difficulty in teaching the subject effectively. Teachers should be knowledgeable in the content areas and pedagogy for which they are responsible to teach, without this, the students may face difficulty in their learning.

Table 10 shows the teachers’ practices in teaching music when taken as a whole was determined using frequency, percentage, and rank.

As the data presented, teachers’ practices when taken as a whole preferred to allowing pupils to find joy and excitement that comes with learning music. This reflects a student- centered approach, where teacher prioritizes creating an emotionally positive environment. When Learners enjoy learning, they are motivated and likely to engage deeply with the subject. Music being a highly emotional and expressive form of art.

This shows that educators should design engaging, interactive lessons that address to the interests of their pupils. Emphasis might be placed on activities that elicit strong emotions, like interactive games, performances, and genre exploration.

This result is supported by the findings of Cartagena, (2021) which states that the play activities, which are natural to children, possess great potential in honing the musical abilities of the learners. By integrating such activities in the classroom instruction, the learner’s learning experience can be more relevant and can likewise help elevate the learning environment which, in turn, can develop the learner’s musical sensitivity and creativity.

This means that incorporating enjoyable activities into classroom teaching is an effective way to promote musical development in learners. Tteachers can create more engaging and meaningful learning experiences. This approach not only makes the curriculum more relevant but also enhances the learning environment.

Table 10. *Teachers’ Practices in teaching music when taken as a whole*

Items	f	%	Rank
Allow my pupils find joy and excitement that comes with learning music.	167	98.2	1
Let my pupils recite the lyrics of the song.	165	97.1	2.5
Use songs to manage group activities, to maintain focus and foster a positive learning environment	165	97.1	2.5
Create a welcoming and comfortable environment in teaching music when entering and leaving a classroom.	164	96.5	4
Demonstrate first the song, then let the pupils replicate what I did and finally, we perform together.	163	95.9	5
Let my learners try it out for themselves and then, provide supportive feedback after explaining a musical concept	162	95.3	6.5
Encourage learners to express themselves and connect with the class material on a personal level	162	95.3	6.5
Integrate technology in my music teaching to enhance learning outcome.	161	94.7	8.5
Use recorded music examples to illustrate how to perform the song correctly	161	94.7	8.5
Always ask my pupils for their current favorite music and take a few minutes to listen to and analyze it in class.	159	93.5	10
Provide my learners with opportunities like performing on stage during the culminating activity.	158	92.2	11
Participate fully in activities and have multiple opportunities to grasp the subject matter.	151	88.8	12
Always show the music score of the song to the learners every time I teach music.	138	81.2	13
Let my pupils copy the given musical score.	135	79.4	14
Let my pupils join the chorale competition for exposure and experience.	131	77.1	15

Table 11 shows the teachers’ practices in teaching music when taken as a whole was determined using frequency, percentage, and rank. As the data presented, teachers in the age group (20-30 years old) preferred to use the tonic solfege system (fixed-do) so that learners can develop perfect pitch, organized classroom environment that enables the learners to acquire music rudiments by exploring through

the sense of touch and let the pupils interpret the song or other aspects of the music through acting, dancing, and singing, while teachers in the age group of (31-40 years old) chose to use props and toys for learners to discover basic musical concepts tied with organized classroom environment that enables the learners to acquire music rudiments by exploring through the sense of touch. Teachers in the age group of (41-50 years old) they practiced the use of use the tonic solfege system (fixed-do) so that learners can develop perfect pitch and show learners how to properly sing the song through modeling. Lastly, teachers in the age group of (51-60 years old) preferred to practice the use of tonic solfege system, use of the voice as the primary instrument for teaching a song, assess musical progress and understanding of my learners through musical independence and discovery and letting the learners create a simple song composition.

This shows that these practices play a crucial role on how to balance the development of fundamental skills with chances for creativity and flexibility in music education, assisting learners is not just gaining technical mastery but also discovering how to enjoy and express themselves thru music. It is therefore imperative to think and create best practices that is engaging and enjoyable and meaningful learning to the learners.

This result is supported by the findings of Barrett, et.,al. (2022). Titled “Best practices for preschool music education: Supporting music-making throughout the day” which states that music is enjoyable for both children and teachers regardless of of age and holds such potential for creating connections between the teachers and children while providing opportunities for learning and discovery and enhancing academic and social skills.

Table 11. Teachers’ Practices in Teaching Music When Classified According to Age

Items	20-30			31-40			41-50			51-60		
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank
MUSIC												
Use hand sign in acquiring pitch, sight reading and learning primary rhythms to the learners.	65	98.5	4.5	44	93.6	4.5	38	97.4	6	18	100.0	4
Use games for plotting notes and rests.	58	87.9	13	32	68.1	15	27	69.2	15	14	77.8	15
Show learners how to properly sing the song through modeling.	63	85.5	9.5	44	93.6	4.5	39	100.0	2	17	94.4	9.5
Let my learners improvise instruments using localize materials and engage in musical activities.	55	83.3	14	37	78.7	13	29	74.4	14	17	94.4	9.5
Incorporate other disciplines to my music teaching.	52	78.8	15	36	76.6	14	31	79.5	12.5	16	88.9	12.5
Use my voice as the primary instrument for teaching a song.	63	95.5	9.5	42	89.4	9	38	97.4	6	18	100.0	4
Use props and toys for learners to discover basic musical concepts.	62	93.9	12	45	95.7	1.5	38	97.4	6	15	83.3	14
Use the tonic solfege system (fixed-do) so that learners can develop perfect pitch.	66	100.0	2	42	89.4	9	39	100	2	18	100.0	4
Organized classroom environment that enables the learners to acquire music rudiments by exploring through the sense of touch.	66	100.0	2	45	95.7	1.5	38	97.4	6	18	100.0	4
Use solfege as ear training in familiarizing the different notes.	63	95.5	9.5	43	91.5	7	35	89.7	11	18	100.0	4
Assess musical progress and understanding of my learners through musical independence and discovery	64	97.0	6.5	38	80.9	12	31	79.5	12.5	18	100.0	4
Let my learners create a simple song composition.	64	7.0	6.5	44	93.6	4.5	38	97.4	6	18	100.0	4
Conduct song analysis by asking pupils about the title, author, time signature and key signature of the song.	65	8.8	4.5	41	87.2	11	39	100.0	2	17	94.4	9.5
Conduct rhythmic syllabication to the learners.	63	5.5	9.5	42	89.4	9	36	92.3	9.5	17	94.4	9.5
Let pupils interpret the song or other aspects of the music through a blend of acting, dancing and singing.	66	100	2	44	93.6	4.5	36	92.3	9.5	16	88.9	12.5

Table 12 shows the teachers’ practices in teaching music when taken as a whole was determined using frequency, percentage, and rank. As the data presented, male teachers preferred to practice of letting the pupils recite the lyrics of the song while those female teachers chose to practice of allowing their pupils to find joy and excitement that come with learning music.

Table 12. Teachers’ practices in teaching music when classified according to sex

Items	Male			Female		
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank
MUSIC						
Let my pupils recite the lyrics of the song.	40	100	1	125	96.2	4.5
Let my pupils join the chorale competition for exposure and experience.	32	80.0	13.5	99	76.2	15
Demonstrate first the song then let the pupils replicate what I did and finally, we perform it together.	39	97.5	3.5	124	95.4	6.5
Always show the music score of the song to the learners everytime I teach music.	32	80.0	13.5	106	81.5	13
Let my pupils copy the given musical score.	30	75.0	15	105	80.8	14
Integrate technology in my music teaching to enhance learning outcomes.	36	90.0	11.5	125	96.2	4.5
Use recorded music examples to illustrate how to perform the song correctly.	37	92.5	9.5	123	94.6	8.5
Use songs to manage group activities, to maintain focus and foster a positive learning environment.	39	97.5	3.5	126	96.9	3
Allow my pupils find joy and excitement that comes with learning music.	39	97.5	3.5	128	98.5	1
Always ask my pupils for their current favorite music and take a few minutes to listen to and analyze it in class.	38	95.5	7	121	93.1	10
Use variety of instructional materials to ensure all my learners can participate fully in activities and have multiple opportunities to grasp the subject matter.	36	90.0	11.5	115	88.5	12
Create a welcoming and comfortable environment in teaching music when entering and leaving a classroom.	37	92.5	9.5	127	97.7	2

Let my learners try it out for themselves and then, provide supportive feedback after explaining a musical concept .	39	97.5	3.5	123	94.6	8.5
Provide my learners with opportunities like performing on stage during the culminating activity.	38	95.0	7	120	92.3	11
Encourage learners to express themselves and connect with the class material on a personal level.	38	95.0	7	124	95.4	6.5

The result shows that male and female teachers bring different strengths to music education, with male teachers focusing more on structures, participatory activities and female teachers emphasizing emotional support and innovation through technology. Each of these approaches have distinction, and when used in conjunction, they can produce a comprehensive and successful music education setting that fosters students' talent and personal development.

This result is supported by the findings of Wiggins (2023) which states that teachers regardless of their sex need to tailor instruction to meet the diverse needs of students is crucial in music education.

This means that music educators must adopt flexible and adaptive teaching approaches to address the diverse needs of their students. By tailoring instruction to accommodate varying musical abilities, interests, and learning styles, teachers can foster a more inclusive and supportive learning environment.

Table 13 shows the teachers' practices in teaching music when taken as a whole was determined using frequency, percentage, and rank.

As the data presented, teachers with bachelor's degree preferred to "use songs to manage group activities, to maintain focus and foster a positive learning environment " and "allow my pupils to find joy and excitement that comes with learning music". Those teachers with master's units chose to practice to "let their pupils recite the lyrics of the song", masters degree holder on the othe hand preferred to practice of demonstrating the song first, the let the pupils replicate what they did and finally , they perform together". Teachers with doctorate units practiced "Demonstrate the song first, then let the pupils replicate what I did, and finally, we perform it together", "Use recorded music examples to illustrate how to perform the song correctly" ,"Use songs to manage group activities, to maintain focus and foster a positive learning environment" and "Allow my pupils to find joy and excitement that comes with learning music". Lastly those teachers with doctorate degree holder chose to "Demonstrate the song first, then let the pupils replicate what I did, and finally, we perform it together", "Use songs to manage group activities, to maintain focus and foster a positive learning environment" and "Provide my learners with opportunities like performing on stage during the culminating activity".

Table 13. Teachers' practices in each music when classified according to educational attainment

Items	Bachelor's Degree			W/Master's Units			Master's Degree			W/ Doctorate Units			Doctorate Degree		
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	F	%	Rank
MUSIC															
Let my pupils recite the lyrics of the song.	90	96.8	6.5	48	98.0	1	23	95.8	4	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Let my pupils join the chorale competition for exposure and experience.	79	84.9	13.5	35	71.4	15	14	58.3	15	2	66.7	14.5	1	100.0	8
Demonstrate first the song then let the pupils replicate what I did and finally, we perform together.	89	95.7	9.5	46	93.9	7.5	24	100.0	1.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Always show the music score of the song to the learners everytime I teach music.	79	84.9	13.5	39	79.6	13	16	66.7	13.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Let my pupils copy the given musical score.	76	81.7	15	36	73.5	14	20	83.3	11	3	66.7	14.5	1	100.0	8
Integrate technology in my music teaching to enhance learning outcomes.	90	96.8	6.5	46	93.9	7.5	21	87.5	8.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Use recorded music examples to illustrate how to perform the song correctly.	86	92.5	11.5	46	93.9	7.5	24	100.0	1.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Use songs to manage group activities, to maintain focus and foster a positive learning environment.	93	100.0	1.5	47	95.9	3	21	87.5	8.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Allow my pupils find joy and excitement that comes with learning music.	93	100.0	1.5	47	95.9	3	23	95.8	4	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Always ask my pupils for their current favorite music and take a few minutes to listen to and analyze it in class.	90	96.8	6.5	46	93.9	7.5	19	79.2	12	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Use variety of instructional materials to ensure all my learners can participate fully in activities and have multiple opportunities to grasp the subject matter.	90	96.8	6.5	41	83.7	12	16	66.7	13.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Create a welcoming and comfortable environment in teaching music when entering and leaving a classroom.	92	98.9	3.5	46	93.9	7.5	22	91.7	6	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Let my learners try it out for themselves and then, provide supportive feedback after explaining a musical concept .	89	95.7	9.5	46	93.9	7.5	23	95.8	4	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Provide my learners with opportunities like performing on stage during the culminating activity.	86	92.5	11.5	47	95.9	3	21	87.5	8.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8
Encourage learners to express themselves and connect with the class material on a personal level.	92	98.9	3.5	45	91.8	11	21	87.5	8.5	3	100.0	7	1	100.0	8

This shows that the methods used by music educators differ depending on their level of education, with more highly qualified educators emphasizing both technical proficiency and student involvement while utilizing a wider variety of instructional resources. While teachers with higher degrees use more sophisticated techniques like technology, records, and performances, those with bachelor's degrees concentrate more on practical classroom management techniques. Since higher education gives instructors the tools they need to create a well-rounded and engaging learning environment for their pupils, this path emphasizes the value of ongoing professional development.

The result of this study is supported by the findings of Nikolai, et.,al (2020) which states that teachers had a strong wish to expand their pedagogical repertoires in order to improve student learning. Therefore, Professional Development should reinforce these needs by familiarising teachers with meaningful pedagogical contents. Such are, for example, multilingual pedagogies, culturally relevant teaching, pedagogies of student voice and empowerment that support teachers in pedagogically conceptualising their practices, and at the same time attempt to avoid Othering by focusing on students and improving student learning.

This means that Professional development programs should comprehensively equip teachers with a broad spectrum of effective pedagogical strategies. By incorporating these methods, educators can enhance their instructional practices, foster inclusive and equitable learning environments, and address the diverse needs of their students.

Table 14 shows the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to congressional district was determined using frequency, percentage, and rank.

As the data presented, first congressional district top-ranked practice was to "Allow my pupils to find joy and excitement that comes with learning music" while second congressional district practice more on the "Use songs to manage group activities, to maintain focus and foster a positive learning environment" and "Create a welcoming and comfortable environment in teaching music when entering and leaving a classroom". Third congressional district of the other hand, preferred to "Let my pupils recite the lyrics of the song", "Demonstrate the song first, then let the pupils replicate what I did and finally, we perform it together" and "Use songs to manage group activities, to maintain focus and foster a positive learning environment".

Furthermore, fourth congressional district's top-ranked practices was to "Let my pupils recite the lyrics of the song", "Integrate technology in my music teaching to enhance learning outcomes" "Use recorded music examples to illustrate how to perform the song correctly". Lastly, fifth congressional district top-ranked practice was to Allow my pupils to find joy and excitement that comes with learning music", "Use recorded music examples to illustrate how to perform the song correctly" and "Use songs to manage group activities, to maintain focus and foster a positive learning environment" This indicated the diversity of music education approaches is reflected in the differences in the top-ranked teaching practices among congressional districts.

Different districts' teachers place varied emphasis on different facets of music education, from traditional approaches and technological integration to classroom management and connection to music. Both the distinct educational environments and the resources that are available in each district are reflected in these strategies. Knowing these district-specific priorities can help guide resource allocation and focused professional development to help teachers provide engaging and successful music education.

This result is supported by the findings McKoy, et.al. (2022). Which states that culturally responsive pedagogy involves teaching in ways that are responsive to how different culturally specific knowledge bases impact learning. It is a pedagogy that recognizes the importance of including students' cultural references Preface in all aspects of learning. Music educators are in a unique position to fully implement these practices in their classrooms given the intimate connection between music and culture.

This means that culturally responsive pedagogy, which integrates students' cultural references into all aspects of learning, is particularly well-suited to music education. Given the deep connection between music and culture, music educators are uniquely positioned to implement these practices, enhancing students' engagement and fostering a more inclusive learning environment.

Table 14. Teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to congressional district

Items	1- District			2- District			3- District			4- district			5- District		
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank
MUSIC															
Let my pupils recite the lyrics of the song.	36	94.7	4.5	35	94.6	5.5	27.00.0	3	3	100.0	2.5	33	97.1	7	
Let my pupils join the chorale competition for exposure and experience.	26	68.4	13.5	30	81.1	13	18	66.7	15	28	82.4	15	29	85.3	14
Demonstrate first the song then let the pupils replicate what I did and finally, we perform it together.	35	92.1	8.5	35	94.6	5.5	27	100.0	3	33	97.1	6	33	97.1	7
Always show the music score of the song to the learners everytime teach music.	26	68.4	13.5	30	81.1	13	21	77.8	13	30	88.2	12	31	91.2	13
Let my pupils copy the given musical score.	29	76.3	15	30	81.1	13	19	70.4	14	29	85.3	13.5	28	82.4	15
Integrate technology in my music teaching to enhance learning outcomes.	36	94.7	4.5	35	94.6	5.5	23	85.2	11.5	34	100.0	2.5	33	97.1	7
Use recorded music examples to illustrate how to perform the song correctly.	34	89.5	11	34	91.9	9.5	25	92.6	9.5	33	97.1	6	34	100.0	2
Use songs to manage group activities, to maintain focus and foster positive learning environment.	36	94.7	4.5	36	97.3	1.5	27	100.0	3	32	94.1	9	34	100.0	2
Allow my pupils find joy and excitement that comes with learning music.	37	97.4	1.5	35	94.6	5.5	27	100.0	3	34	100.0	2.5	34	100.0	2
Always ask my pupils for their current favorite music and take a few minutes to listen to and analyze it in class.	36	94.7	4.5	34	91.9	9.5	25	92.6	9.5	31	91.2	11	33	97.1	7
Use variety of instructional materials to ensure all my learners can participate fully in activities and have multiple opportunities to gras the subject matter.	31	81.6	12	33	89.2	12	26	96.3	7	29	85.3	13.5	32	94.1	11.5
Create a welcoming and comfortable environment in teaching music when entering and leaving a classroom.	35	92.1	8.5	36	97.3	1.5	26	96.3	7	34	100.0	2.5	33	97.1	7
Let my learners try it out for themselves and then, provide supportive feedback after explaining a musical concept .	37	97.4	1.5	34	91.9	9.5	27	100.0	3	32	94.1	9	32	94.1	11.5
Provide my learners with opportunities like performing on stage during the culminating activity.	35	92.1	8.5	35	94.6	5.5	23	85.2	11.5	32	94.1	9	33	97.1	7
Encourage learners to express themselves and connect with the class material on a personal level.	35	92.1	8.5	35	94.6	5.5	26	96.3	7	33	97.1	6	33	97.1	7

Table 15 shows the teachers' practices in teaching Music when classified according to specialization was determined using frequency, percentage, and rank.

As the data presented, general education teachers top- ranked practice in teachin music was to Allow my pupils to find joy and excitement that comes with learning music, core subject teachers on the other hand, preferred to practice in the Use songs to manage group activities, to maintain focus and foster a positive learning environment.

This shows that the various approaches to music education are highlighted by the variations in teaching strategies between teachers of General Education and Core Subjects. While Core Subject teachers concentrate more on technical proficiency and performance abilities, General Education teachers place a higher priority on fostering an inclusive and emotionally supportive learning environment. Knowing these distinctions can assist teachers in creating more thorough and successful music education plans that meet the needs of every student, irrespective of background or area of expertise.

This result is supported by the findings of Suson, et., al. (2020). Which states that teachers must recognize that learners at school do not have similar attitudes and abilities in coping up from their class. Teachers need to provide more activities and learning techniques through differentiated instruction for the learners to enhance their reading comprehension skills no matter what intelligences they have.

This means that educators should employ a variety of teaching strategies tailored to individual learners' needs. By doing so, they can create an equitable learning environment where all students have the opportunity to develop essential skills, such as reading comprehension, regardless of their inherent intelligences or learning styles.

Table 15. Teachers' Practices in teaching music when classified according to Specialization

Items	General Education			Core Subject		
	f	%	Rank	f	%	Rank
MUSIC						
Let my pupils recite the lyrics of the song.	113	97.4	2	52	96.3	7.5
Let my pupils join the chorale competition for exposure and experience.	91	78.4	15	40	74.1	14
Demonstrate first the song then let the pupils replicate what I did and finally, we perform it together.	110	94.8	7.5	53	98.1	3.5
Always show the music score of the song to the learners everytime I teach music.	99	85.3	13	39	72.2	15
Let my pupils copy the given musical score.	93	80.2	14	42	77.8	13
Integrate technology in my music teaching to enhance learning outcomes.	109	94.0	7.5	52	96.3	7.5
Use recorded music examples to illustrate how to perform the song correctly.	107	92.2	10	53	98.1	3.5
Use songs to manage group activities, to maintain focus and foster a positive learning environment.	111	95.7	4.5	54	100.0	1
Allow my pupils find joy and excitement that comes with learning music.	114	98.3	1	53	98.1	3.5
Always ask my pupils for their current favorite music and take a few minutes to listen to and analyze it in class.	109	94.0	7.5	50	92.6	11
Use variety of instructional materials to ensure all my learners can participate fully in activities and have multiple opportunities to grasp the subject matter.	105	90.5	12	46	85.2	12
Create a welcoming and comfortable environment in teaching music when entering and leaving a classroom.	112	96.6	3	52	96.3	7.5
Let my learners try it out for themselves and then, provide supportive feedback after explaining a musical concept .	109	94.0	7.5	53	98.1	3.5
Provide my learners with opportunities like performing on stage during the culminating activity.	106	91.4	11	52	96.3	7.5
Encourage learners to express themselves and connect with the class material on a personal level.	111	95.7	4.5	51	94.4	10

Table 16 shows the differences in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, Congressional District and speciallization were determined using chi-square.

It shows that there was no significant difference in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to age with the chi-square value of 5.403 and a p-value of 0.145. The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to age. This showed that ages 21 to 30 of teachers' pedagogical approaches does not significantly differ from 31 to 40, 41 to 50 and 51 to 60 years old. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to age was not rejected.

In terms of sex, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to sex with the chi- square value of 0.768 and a p-value of 0.381. The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no no significant difference in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to sex. This showed that male teachers' pedagogical approaches does not significantly differ from 31 female. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to sex was not rejected.

Moreover, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to educational attainment with the chi-square value of 9.768 and a p-value of 0.045. The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to educational attainment. This showed that teachers' pedagogical approaches who were bachelors degree holder, does not significantly differ from those with master's units, master's degree holder, those with doctorate units and

doctorate degree holder. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to educational attainment was not rejected.

Furthermore, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to congressional district with the chi-square value of 1.366 and a p-value of 0.850. The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to educational attainment. This showed that teachers' pedagogical approaches who were in the first congressional districts, does not significantly differ from those of second, third, fourth and fifth congressional district. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to congressional district was not rejected.

In terms of specialization, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to specialization with the chi-square value of 0.938 and a p-value of 0.333. The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to specialization. This showed that teachers' pedagogical approaches of generalist teacher does not significantly differ from core subject teachers. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to specialization was not rejected.

This result is supported by the findings of Brown and Lee (2023). Which states that for teachers to effectively and enrichingly teach music to their pupils, their pedagogical approaches and content understanding are essential teachers to use the latest tools available in their work to engage students. To engage students in learning, one needs to be innovative and new ideas should be introduced so that students get excited about what they are learning. The use of varied and latest pedagogical approaches like technology integration in music education.

Table 16. *Significant Difference in the Teachers' Pedagogical Approaches in Teaching Music When Classified According to Age, Sex, Educational Attainment, Congressional District and Specialization*

Variables	Chi-square Value	p-value	Remarks
Age	5.403	0.145	Not Significant
Sex	0.768	0.381	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	9.768	0.045	Not Significant
Congressional District	1.366	0.850	Not Significant
Specialization	0.938	0.333	Not Significant

p > 0.05 Not Significant

Table 17 shows the differences in the teachers' content knowledge in teaching music when classified according to age, educational attainment, and congressional district were determined using Kruskal Wallis H-Test.

It shows that there was no significant differences in the level of teachers' content knowledge in teaching music when classified according to age with the H-test value of 0.914 and a p-value of 0.822. The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the level of teachers' content knowledge in teaching music when classified according to age. This showed that the content knowledge teachers aged 20 to 30 does not significantly differ from teachers aged 31 to 40, 41 to 50 and 51 to 60 years old. Therefore, the null hypotheses which stated that there was no significant difference in the content knowledge of teachers in teaching music when classified according to age was not rejected.

Moreover, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the teachers' content knowledge in teaching music when classified according educational attainment with the H-test value of 3.462 and p-value 0.484. The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the level of teachers' content knowledge of teachers in music when classified according to educational attainment. This showed that content knowledge of music teachers who were bachelor's degree does not significantly differ from teachers who were bachelor's degree holder with master's units, master's degree holder, doctorate units and doctorate degree holder. Therefore, the null hypotheses which stated that there was no significant difference in the content knowledge of teachers in teaching music when classified according to educational attainment was not rejected.

Furthermore, the result shows that there was significant difference in the teachers' content knowledge in teaching music when classified according congressional district with the H-test value of 13.948 and p-value of 0.007. The p-value was less than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was significant difference in the level of content knowledge in teaching music when classified according to congressional district. This showed that the content knowledge of teachers in teaching music who were in the first congressional district does significantly differ from those who were in second, third, fourth and fifth congressional districts. Therefore, the null hypotheses which stated that there was no significant difference in the content knowledge of teachers in teaching music when classified according to congressional district was rejected.

The result conforms to the findings of Özgür, (2020) which states that regardless of age, and educational background, the content knowledge of teachers remained high. This suggests that content knowledge is not significantly influenced by age, and educational

background.

Similarly, the results show no significant difference in content knowledge based on age. The uniformity in teachers’ content knowledge across different age groups suggested effective training and professional development programs that cater to all age demographics. Age does not affect the professional standards upheld by teachers , ensuring that music teachers, regardless of age, were equally committed to their job.

Moreover, the analysis reveals no significant difference in the level of teachers’ content knowledge according to educational attainment. The content knowledge with a bachelor’s degree, those with units towards a master’s degree, and those with a master’s degree, those with doctorate units a is similarly high. The findings showed that educational background does not significantly influence the content knowledge of teachers in teaching music, indicating that the content knowledge of teachers are upheld uniformly regardless of educational attainment. This could reflect the efficacy of standardized training programs that ensure all officials meet high professional standards.

Furthermore, the findings showed significant difference in teachers’ content knowledge based on the congressional district. This indicated that teachers in the first congressional district displayed high content knowledge in teaching music compared to the other districts. This shows that each congressional district should engage more trainings and seminars to teachers in order to improve the level of their content knowledge in teaching music.

This result is supported by the findings of Manila, (2020) in his study on“ Pedagogical content knowledge in music education among public elementary teachers” where he suggested that there is a need to capacitate teachers and enhance their knowledge on the content and pedagogy in music education. Teachers should have mastery of the contents of music curriculum in the elementary level as well as the knowledge of different methods and strategies that they may use in teaching those contents.

Table 17. Significant Differences in the Level of Teachers’ Content Knowledge in Teaching Music When Classified According to Age, Educational Attainment and Congressional District

Variables	N	Mean Rank	H-test	Df	p-value	Remarks
Age						
20-30	66	88.30	.914	3	.822	Not Significant
31-40	47	79.77				
41-50	39	86.74				
51-60	18	87.53				
Educational Attainment						
Bachelor’s Degree	93	83.29	3.462	4	.484	Not Significant
W/ Masters Units	49	93.26				
Master’s Degree	24	78.98				
W/ Doctorate Units	3	98.83				
Doctorate Degree	1	27.50				
Congressional District						
1st District	38	95.01	13.948	4	.007	Significant
2nd District	37	61.31				
3rd District	27	101.19				
4th District	34	82.25				
5th District	34	91.99				

p>0.05 Not Significant

Table 18 shows the differences in the level teachers’ content knowledge in teaching music when classified according to age, educational attainment, and Congressional District were determined using Mann Whitney U-Test.

It shows that there was no significant difference in the level of teachers’ content knowledge when classified according to the sex with a U-test value of 2472.000 and a p-value of 0.637. The p–value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the level of teachers’ content knowledge when classified according to the sex. This showed that the level of content knowledge does not significantly differ from male and female. This shows that sex does not play a role in how much content knowledge teachers possess in music .Therefore the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the level of content knowledge in teaching music when classified according to sex was not rejected.

Moreover, the analysis reveals no significant difference in the level of teachers’ content knowledge according to specialization with a U-test value of 2980.500 and p-value of 0.611. The p–value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the level of teachers’ content knowledge when classified according to the specialization. This showed that the level of content knowledge does not significantly differ from generalist and core subject teachers. Therefore the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the level of content knowledge in teaching music when classified according to specialization was not rejected.

The result conforms to the findings of Özgür, (2020) that states that regardless of sex and specialization, the content knowledge of teachers teaching music remained consistently high. This suggests that teachers' content knowledge is not significantly influenced by their sex or their specialization. The findings of this comprehensive study shed light on the commendable content knowledge displayed by teachers teaching music. The results indicate that these teachers are dedicated and committed to deliver lessons to the learners.

This shows that sex does not play a role in how much content knowledge teachers possess in music. This further noted that both male and female teachers are equipped in terms of content knowledge. As to the specialization the results show that teachers' content knowledge in teaching music is consistent regardless of their area of specialization whether or not a teacher specializes in music or another subject does not impact their level of content knowledge in teaching music. Moreover, the results further show that the interventions to improve music content knowledge should focus on areas other than sex and specialization.

Table 18. *Significant Difference in the Teachers' Content Knowledge in Teaching Music When Classified According to Sex, and Specialization*

Variables	N	Mean	Sum of ranks	U-test	p-value	Remarks
			Rank			
Sex						
Male	40	88.70	3548.00	2472.000	.637	Not Significant
Female	130	84.52	10987.00			
Specialization						
General Education	116	86.81	10069.50	2980.500	.611	Not Significant
Core subjects	54	82.69	4465.50			

p > 0.05 Not Significant

Table 19 shows the differences in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, Congressional District and specialization were determined using chi-square.

It shows that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to age with the chi-square value of 6.992 and a p-value of 0.072. The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to age. This showed that ages 21 to 30 of teachers' pedagogical approaches does not significantly differ from 31 to 40, 41 to 50 and 51 to 60 years old. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to age was not rejected.

In terms of sex, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to sex with the chi-square value of 0.01 and a p-value of 0.920. The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to sex. This showed that male teachers' practices does not significantly differ from female. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to sex was not rejected.

Moreover, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to educational attainment with the chi-square value of 3.562 and a p-value of 0.469. The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to educational attainment. This showed that teachers' practices who were bachelors degree holder, does not significantly differ from those with master's units, master's degree holder, those with doctorate units and doctorate degree holder. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to educational attainment was not rejected.

Furthermore, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to congressional district with the chi-square value of 2.746 and a p-value of 0.601. The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to congressional district. This showed that teachers' practices in the first congressional districts, does not significantly differ from those of second, third, fourth and fifth congressional district. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to congressional district was not rejected.

In terms of specialization, the result shows that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to specialization with the chi-square value of 0.127 and a p-value of 0.721. The p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to specialization. This showed that teachers' practices of generalist teacher does not significantly differ from core subject teachers. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to specialization was not rejected.

This result is supported by the study of Campbell et., al (2021) Which states that choosing to engage in practices that may be perceived as "risky," both within and beyond contexts of rapid change, may help educators build their own sense of identity as capable, creative,

and responsive professionals.

Table 19. *Significant Difference in the Teachers' Practices in Teaching Music When Classified According to Age, Sex, Educational Attainment, Congressional District and Specialization*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Chi-square Value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Age	6.992	.072	Not Significant
Sex	0.01	.920	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	3.562	.469	Not Significant
Congressional District	2.746	.601	Not Significant
Specialization	0.127	.721	Not Significant

p>0.05 Not Significant

Significant relationships among teachers' pedagogical approaches, content knowledge, and practices in teaching music was determined using Spearman rho.

Table 20 shows that there was a significant relationship between the level of teacher's pedagogical approaches and content knowledge in teaching music. The Spearman rho value was 0.461 with a p-value of 0.000. The p-value was less than 0.05 level of significance which meant that there was a significant relationship between the level of teachers' pedagogical approaches and content knowledge. This showed that when the level of teachers' pedagogical approaches was high, the content knowledge were also high. The results denoted strong and substantial correlation. The null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical approaches and content knowledge in teaching music is rejected.

This result supported by the finding of Bautista and Fautley, (2021) which states that teachers with deep subject knowledge were better able to design effective lessons, respond to student needs, and facilitate higher levels of student engagement and learning.

The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between teachers' pedagogical approaches and content knowledge among teachers teaching music. This strong correlation suggested that teachers who demonstrated high levels of pedagogical approaches also exhibited strong content knowledge in teaching music. The results underscored the interconnectedness between these two key attributes, showing that a commitment to upholding classroom standards, translated into effective delivery of content knowledge to the learners. This correlation highlighted the importance of cultivating a well rounded teachers where pedagogical approaches served as fundamental attributes for ensuring efficient and effective content knowledge delivery.

Also, there was a significant relationship between the teachers' pedagogical approaches and practices in teaching music. The Spearman rho value was 0.193 with a p-value of 0.012. The p-value was less than 0.05 level of significant meant that there was a significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical approaches and practices in teaching music. This showed that when the level of pedagogical approaches was high the practices in teaching music was also high. The results denoted a moderate correlation between variables.

The null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship between the teachers' pedagogical approaches and practices in teaching music is rejected.

The result conforms to the findings of Cartagena (2021) which states that teachers with deep subject knowledge were better able to design effective lessons, respond to student's interests can be effective learning facilitator.

The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between teachers' pedagogical approaches and practices among teachers teaching music. This suggested that teachers should exhibit strong pedagogical approaches so that they could also showed best practices in teaching music. The weak correlation showed that while pedagogical approaches contributes significantly to practices, other factors also influenced among teachers.

In like manner, there was a significant relationship between the content knowledge and the practices in teaching music. The Spearman rho value was 0.170 with a p-value of 0.027. The p-value was less than 0.05 level of significant meant that there was a significant relationship between teachers' content knowledge and practices in teaching music. This showed that when the level of content knowledge was high the practices in teaching music was also high. The results denoted a weak correlation between variables.

The null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship between the teachers' content knowledge and practices in teaching music is rejected.

The result conforms to the study of Suson (2020) which states that teachers who have demonstrated mastery in content knowledge can create best practices in teaching music. He also added that teachers need to provide more activities and learning techniques through differentiated instruction for the learners to enhance their skills no matter what intelligences they have.

This means that effective music education depends on teachers' ability to blend their understanding of music with appropriate teaching strategies. Strong content knowledge ensures accurate and deep instruction, while varied pedagogical approaches engage diverse learners and foster creativity.

These results emphasize the importance of fostering best practices among teachers teaching music, as it not only enhanced the

effectiveness of strategies but also strengthened their commitment through practice ensuring quality teaching and learning of the learners especially in teaching music. These findings highlighted and intertwined nature of content knowledge and practices in shaping the learners holistically.

Table 20. *Significant Relationship Among The Teachers' Pedagogical Approaches, Content Knowledge and Practices in Teaching Music*

<i>Correlations</i>	<i>Pedagogical Approaches</i>	<i>Content Knowledge</i>	<i>Practices</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Pedagogical Approaches	rho-Value p-value N	.170* .027 170		Significant
Content Knowledge	rho-Value p-value N		.193* .012 170	Significant
Practices	rho-value p-value N	.416** .000 170		Significant

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Majority of the teachers teaching music in the Schools Division of Iloilo Province were 20-30 years old, female, with bachelor's degree and most of them in the first congressional district with general education specialization.

The teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music with each group contributing distinct strengths and perspectives to the classroom, music teaching can vary greatly depending on the age of the teacher. The most frequently employed pedagogical approach among music educators was integration with other disciplines. Teachers at all educational levels value interdisciplinary approaches, and more experienced teachers are more likely to use practical, hands-on methods, reflecting advancement in teaching expertise as educational attainment upgraded. Male respondents opted to incorporate other disciplines into their music teaching and use their voice as the primary instrument for teaching a song, while female respondents made the same choice. The districts have certain commonalities, like interdisciplinary instruction, and the top-ranked strategies used in each district represent localization and preferences in music education. These variations provide information about how geographical context may influence instructional methods and learning objectives. While core teachers give a more comprehensive, integrative approach, general education teachers choose a simpler teaching style.

The level of teachers' content knowledge in teaching music when taken as a whole was high. The high level of content knowledge in teaching music is consistent across different demographic categories including age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district and specialization. Males marginally outperform females, and the age range of 41- 50 has the highest results. Doctorate holders score lower in content knowledge than teachers with master's or doctoral degrees. When comparing districts, the third district exhibits the best top understanding, while both General Education and Core Subjects continue to score highly by specialization.

Teachers' practices in teaching music vary across demographics. Teachers aged 20–30 use the tonic solfège system with creative, hands-on activities; those aged 31–40 incorporate tactile learning with props; ages 41–50 focus on pitch development through solfège and singing models; and ages 51–60 emphasize vocal skills, songwriting, and independent assessment. Male teachers tend to focus on structure and participatory activities, while female teachers emphasize emotional support and technology-driven innovation. Educators with advanced degrees integrate technical and student-centered approaches, using tools like technology and performances, while bachelor's-level teachers prioritize practical classroom management. District specific practices align with local priorities, but interdisciplinary teaching is common. General education teachers prioritize inclusivity, while core subject teachers emphasize technical skills and performance.

There were no significant differences in the teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching music when classified according to age ($X^2=5.403$, $p=0.145$) sex ($X^2=0.768$, $p=0.381$), educational attainment ($X^2=9.768$, $p=0.45$) congressional district ($X^2=1.366$, $p=0.850$) and specialization ($X^2=0.938$, $p=0.333$)

There was no significant differences in the level of teachers' content knowledge in teaching music when classified according to age ($H=0.914$, $p=0.822$) sex ($U=2472.000$, $p=0.637$), educational attainment ($H=3.462$, $p=0.484$) and specialization ($U=2980.500$, $p=0.611$). However there was a significant difference existed terms of congressional district ($H=13.948$, $p=0.007$).

There were no significant differences in the teachers' practices in teaching music when classified according to age ($X^2=6.992$, $p=0.072$), sex ($X^2=0.01$, $p=0.920$), educational attainment ($X^2=3.562$, $p=0.469$), congressional district ($X^2=2.746$, $p=0.601$) and specialization ($X^2=0.127$, $p=0.721$).

There was a significant relationships between the teachers' pedagogical approaches and content knowledge, ($\rho=0.416$, $p=0.000$), Pedagogical approaches and practices ($r=0.193$, $p=0.012$), and content knowledge and practices ($r=0.170$, $p=0.027$) among teachers who were teaching music.

Conclusions

The demographic profile highlighted the diversity and dedication within the teaching community, showcasing a blend of educational attainment, professional experience, and commitment to their roles as educators. Such diversity enriched the field by bringing varied perspectives and expertise, contributing to the overall professionalism and effectiveness of the approaches, mastering their content knowledge and practices. These insights underscored the importance of continuing support for professional development.

The teachers, teaching music exhibit expertise and dedication in their role. They are all knowledgeable about the pedagogical approaches in delivering the lesson to the learners, possess high content knowledge, and knows how to practice, regardless of age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization. These findings emphasized the dedication of teachers within congressional districts, highlighting their capacity to manage class and delivers quality learnings that the learners truly deserve. These insights emphasized the importance of sustaining support for professional development initiatives and fostering a collaborative environment in the schools division of iloilo.

Teachers possess knowledge in music, confidently teaching most concepts with few areas for improvement needed to reach full mastery. They demonstrated a remarkably high level of content knowledge across various demographic categories. Whether categorized by age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization. These results highlighted the competence and organizational prowess of teachers within the community in the division, highlighting their ability to ensure smooth operations and successful delivery of the lesson. It emphasized the importance of continuous training and support initiatives to further enhance pedagogical approaches, content knowledge and practices, thereby maintaining the quality teaching and learning.

In terms of practices, It was evident that teachers, who handle music in the schools division of iloilo, exhibited a notably best practices through commitment across various demographic categories. Whether classified by age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district and specialization. They consistently demonstrated dedication to their responsibilities and duties. These findings underscored the steadfast dedication and passion within the division and congressional district, highlighting their crucial role in fostering integrity and quality education.

It is apparent that teachers, teaching music exhibited consistent in pedagogical approaches across various demographic classifications, including age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization. The absence of significant differences suggested a cohesive and uniform approach to pedagogy within the teachers' community in the school division of iloilo. Possible contributing factors could include training programs, stringent organizational policies, and collaborative efforts to upholding professional standards. These insights underlined the effectiveness of current practices in maintaining high levels of quality teaching. The findings emphasized the importance of sustaining these practices and fostering a supportive environment to further enhance pedagogy within school community.

Teachers, teaching music in the Schools Division of Iloilo Province demonstrated a consistent level of content knowledge across various demographic categories, including age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization. The lack of significant differences highlighted a uniformity in the proficiency of content knowledge among teachers in the schools division of iloilo. This was attributed to standardized training programs, effective organizational protocols, and a shared commitment to excellence and collaboration. These findings showed the capability and resiliency of teachers despite the subject alignment. The importance of maintaining and enhancing pedagogical approaches was emphasized to sustain high levels of content knowledge and support continued growth and development of teachers in the field of education.

The teachers, teaching music exhibit expertise and dedication in their role. They are all knowledgeable about teaching practices in delivering the lesson to the learners, possess high content knowledge, and knows how to practice, regardless of age, sex, educational attainment, congressional district, and specialization. These findings emphasized the dedication of teachers within congressional districts, highlighting their capacity to handle class and delivers quality learnings that the learners truly deserve. These findings emphasized the importance of sustaining support for professional development initiatives and fostering a collaborative environment in the schools division of iloilo.

The identified correlations highlight that as pedagogical approaches increase, so as content knowledge and practices levels among these teachers teaching music. This interconnectedness showed the holistic nature of their roles, where pedagogical approaches influences the ability to effectively deliver content knowledge and contribute best practices to their responsibilities within schools division of Iloilo. These findings suggested that enhancing one aspect, such as pedagogical approaches through training, positively impacted both content knowledge and practices, thereby contributing to overall efficiency and effectiveness in the organization and execution of teaching and learning process. Fostering these interconnections through integrated training programs and supportive organizational policies can further elevate the standards and performance of teachers in the Schools Division of Iloilo.

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